

2022 Annual Meeting

Seismological Society of America
Technical Sessions
19–23 April • Bellevue, Washington

The SSA 2022 Annual Meeting is its first in-person gathering since 2019 and will convene at the Hyatt Regency Bellevue, featuring more than 750 technical oral and poster presentations, plenary sessions, workshops, special interest groups and field trips.

The following schedule of events and abstracts are valid until 22 March 2022 and subject to change.

Annual Meeting Co-Chairs

The Society is grateful to the SSA 2022 Co-chairs Jackie Caplan-Auerbach, Western Washington University, and David Schmidt, University of Washington.

Contact

info@seismosoc.org

Technical Program

Plenary Sessions

Keynote Address: The Cascadia Margin Revealed

Tuesday, 19 April, 5:30–6:30 PM

Suzanne Carbotte of Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory

The keynote lecture by Suzanne Carbotte will focus on new research being conducted in Cascadia and will feature recent active source surveys of the Juan de Fuca plate and Cascadia margin and the new scientific insights that these data provide.

Science and Technology from a Makah Perspective—Incorporation of Native American Knowledge Systems

Wednesday, 20 April, 11:30 AM–12:30 PM

Janine Ledford, Executive Director of the Makah Cultural and Research Center

The Future of Subduction Zone Science

Wednesday, 20 April, 6–7 PM

Panelists: John Power, U.S. Geological Survey; Laura Wallace, GNS Science, University of Texas, Austin; S. Shawn Wei, doi: 10.1785/0220220087

Michigan State University. Moderated by Anne Sheehan, University of Colorado, Boulder

Subduction zones host a range of seismic phenomena, including the world's largest earthquakes along the megathrust, in-slab and deep-focus earthquakes, shallow crustal events, tremor and volcanic seismicity. The structure and behavior of subduction systems provides insight into Earth's evolution and plate tectonic processes. A panel will present their vision for the future of subduction zone science and discuss the important next steps to expand our understanding of subduction processes.

SSA President's Address and Awards Ceremony

Thursday, 21 April, 11:30 AM–12:30 PM

SSA President Peggy Hellweg will preside over the awards ceremony and provide an update on the Society. Immediate Past President John Townend (2021–22) will deliver the presidential address. The 2021 honorees:

- William Ellsworth, Harry Fielding Reid Medal
- Seyed Mostafa Mousavi, Charles F. Richter Early Career Award
- Timothy Ahern, Frank Press Public Service Award

Joyner Lecture: A Futurist's View of Earthquake Impact Estimation

Thursday, 21 April, 6–7 PM

David J. Wald, U.S. Geological Survey

Estimating impacts due to earthquakes—whether rapidly for emerging disasters or planning for future scenarios—entails the direct interface of seismological and civil engineering expertise and tools. Both endeavors require considering uncertain models and data since the main components of loss estimation—namely shaking, exposure and vulnerabilities—entail inherent uncertainties. Since actionable response or planning requires confidence in our results, improvements in our loss calculations require continued collaboration. Fortunately, advancements in remote sensing, rapid in-situ monitoring and impact reporting, and machine learning—combined with new datasets such as global building footprints and inventories—allow for innovative data-fusion strategies that integrate with existing models and should significantly improve the accuracy and spatial resolution of rapid shaking